

GUIDEBOOK OF PRACTICES

Regarding
the
recognition
of student
engagement

europ^ean
* Student Engagement Project
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About European STEP

European Student Engagement Project (European STEP is a European project that questions the role of youth engagement in Europe. In the current European context where the active participation of young people in society is highlighted through the EU's Youth Strategy for 2019-2027¹ and mechanisms such as the European Solidarity Corps², the question of recognising young people's engagement arises. Therefore, it was launched to reflect upon the recognition of student engagement in European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).

Since September 2018, the French student associations network, **Animafac**³, has been coordinating the Erasmus +

European Student Engagement Project (European STEP)⁴, in cooperation with six European partners: **the European University Foundation (EUF)** in Luxembourg⁵, **the Office of Student Life of Dublin City University in Ireland**⁶, **the CY Cergy Paris University in France**⁷, **the University of Valladolid in Spain**⁸, **the University of Vienna in Austria**⁹ and **the Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw** in Poland¹⁰.

Moreover, four associated partners are involved in the project to ensure the dissemination of the project and its results: the French Conference of Grandes Ecoles (CGE)¹¹, the French Conference of University Presidents (CPU)¹², the Crous¹³ and the European University Association (EUA)¹⁴.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/youth/policy/youth-strategy_en

² https://europa.eu/youth/solidarity_en

³ <https://www.animafac.net/>

⁴ The European STEP project is an Erasmus+ co-funded strategic partnership project, for the period of September 2018 to June 2021

⁵ <https://uni-foundation.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.dcu.ie/studentlife/office-of-student-life>

⁷ <https://www.u-cergy.fr/en/index.html>

⁸ <https://www.observal.es/es/>

⁹ <https://www.univie.ac.at/en/>

¹⁰ <https://wolontariat.uw.edu.pl/volunteers/>

¹¹ <https://www.cge.asso.fr/>

¹² <http://www.cpu.fr/presentation/presentation-of-the-cpu/>

¹³ <https://www.etudiant.gouv.fr/pid33797/cnous-crous.html>

¹⁴ <https://eua.eu/>

Partners of the project

Associated partners

The previous studies

In order to have a good understanding of the recognition of student engagement, **three studies were led**. The first one consists of a map of the national legislative frameworks for student engagement recognition¹⁵, and the second one is a Preliminary Report based on a survey disseminated to European universities concerning the recognition measures and policies set in their institution¹⁶. The third study was conducted on the basis of interviews with students, teachers and administrative staff members on their perceptions of student engagement and its recognition, and on the effect recognition can have on engagement paths. The results of the studies are available on STEP's website¹⁷.

The following guide has been elaborated based on the previous work led since 2018. It aims to give an overview of the different practices implemented in HEIs concerning student engagement recognition.

¹⁵European Student Engagement Project (2019). Mapping of policy frameworks for student engagement recognition in Europe here: <https://www.animafac.net/minisite/european-step/european-step-en/>

¹⁶European Student Engagement Project(2019). *How European Higher Education Institutions Recognise Student Engagement. European STEP Survey Report* www.asso.li/stepsurveyreport

¹⁷European STEP's website: <https://www.animafac.net/minisite/european-step/european-step-en/>

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Introduction

When you are a student, being engaged in another activity aside from your studies is a way to meet people, to make new experiences, to acquire new skills and competencies, or support a cause dear to you. But it can also be a challenge to balance between academic work and these activities. However, your studies and your engagement do not necessarily have to be in opposition to each other and can be recognised as complementary. When recognised by higher education institutions, ***engagement can play a more important role in your studies and be valued as a more practical experience of learning and development.***

When you are working in an institution, implementing practices regarding the recognition of student engagement is just as important. This creates the opportunity for students to develop skills and competencies complementary to the academic knowledge they acquire during their studies. ***More than better preparing students for their professional life, this is also a way to encourage students to get engaged in the community and become better citizens.*** Thus, recognising student engagement will help higher

education institutions carry out their societal mission while strengthening students as future professionals and individuals.

We hope that students and staff members of Higher Education Institutions will use this guidebook **to find inspirational examples** of what can be done to recognise student engagement in their own institution.

In this guidebook, you can also find **tools to assess the practices** implemented by a specific institution, as well as guidelines on how to use ***them in order to bring about successful and sustainable change in your institution regarding student engagement recognition.***

Part I

Overview of what student engagement is

What is student engagement?

The previous studies of the project showed that **there is no single definition of student engagement across Europe**, so because of the many forms it can take, it is to be understood in a broad sense. You can be engaged inside your university, as a students' representative, as a mentor or in one of the university associations, or outside your university in an NGO. Being involved in cultural or sports activities can also be recognised by your university¹⁸.

An engagement can be regular, over months or even years, but can also be episodic when it comes to organising an event or a

¹⁸European Student Engagement Project (2020). *A Qualitative study: Crossed perspectives on student engagement and its recognition in European higher education institutions*: <https://www.animafac.net/media/O3-Report-English.pdf>

¹⁹European Student Engagement Project (2019). *How European Higher Education Institutions Recognise Student Engagement. European STEP Survey Report* www.asso.li/stepsurveyreport

workshop. However, according to the sample of HEIs surveyed for the previous part of the European STEP¹⁹, the most commonly recognised level of engagement was found to be regular engagement. And because there is no consensus between countries and even among universities on what student engagement is, not every type of engagement cited above is recognised by all universities.

Why do students get engaged in extracurricular activities?

The previous study²⁰ on the perceptions of students and other members of HEIs showed that **there were several reasons for students to get engaged**. Based on the typology of Claire Thoury in her thesis on student engagement²¹, the study outlined five non-exclusive categories:

²⁰ European Student Engagement Project (2020), *ibid*

²¹Claire Thoury, *Student engagement in a world of individualisation: identity construction and political careers.*, Sociology. Université Sorbonne Paris Cité, 2017. In her thesis, Claire Thoury presents the following typology: commitment as a bandage, commitment to Christian charity, commitment with a professionalising vocation, commitment as a response "to identity trials" (Dubet, François, Martuccelli, Danilo, *Dans quelle société vivons-nous*,

- **To build an identity** and better face one's problems or doubts, engagement can be very fulfilling. By participating in a project or supporting a cause, students can socialise and learn to know themselves better.
- **To help a cause** close to your ideals and improve society. These engagements may be of political nature, but students are not necessarily politically engaged. For example, they can be environmental, social, activists or anti-poverty.
- **To be useful** by giving some time and energy. There is a sense of charity in this perception of engagement in which students get involved to help people or serve the community.
- **To gain some confidence and skills** to prepare yourself and facilitate the integration into the labour market. Engagement is seen as complementary to the studies and is a way to improve your resume.
- **To be part of something bigger** and meet other people around a common project

Thus, to carry out an engagement can be the result of different motivations and most of the time students do not wait for recognition to do so.

However, the recognition of an engagement by an institution is a form **of legitimation** that can encourage some students to continue their engagement and can be an incentive for others to get engaged.

The purpose of this Guidebook is to help engaged students and HEIs improve their practices or implement new ones to recognise student engagement. If changes occur, involving students in the process and communicating about it can be a great way of creating momentum to encourage more students to engage.

Editions du Seuil, 1998). Based on our sample, we have identified certain similar types of commitment and adapted the typology accordingly. We did not find the last two types of commitment in this typology.

Part II

Universities' practices in recognising engagement

Why is it important for universities to recognise engagement?

The recognition of student engagement can mean many things: **to value, to reward, to promote, to enhance**, etc. And these different notions can be translated into different practices, from the introduction of an elective module on student engagement to the deliverance of a certificate of acquired skills, and many others that are presented in this guidebook.

But more than benefitting engaged students, HEIs can also find value in it. Indeed, as mentioned in the qualitative study²², some of them underline that this is a way for them to accomplish what some

refer to as the “**third mission**” of HEIs. If universities used to have two missions which are producing knowledge and disseminating it through teaching, some of them **endorse a third mission which is to play an active and direct role in society as a driving force for socio-economic development**. That is to say helping students become concerned citizens and preparing them for the job market as well as being an active stakeholder in the development of the community. Thus, promoting student engagement, accompanying them, and recognising the skills and competencies they acquire is a way for universities to better carry out their “third mission”.

From the sample of European HEIs surveyed for the Preliminary Report²³ - a previous study of the project - a majority of universities indicated that encouraging student engagement was part of their strategic plan, often referring to the third mission. **However, recognition measures are still rather new, and developing good practices that are valued by students can be a way to stay competitive/stand out as an HEI and attract more students.**

²²European Student Engagement Project (2020). *A Qualitative study: Crossed perspectives on student engagement and its recognition in European higher education institutions*: <https://www.animafac.net/media/O3-Report-English.pdf>

²³European Student Engagement Project (2019). *How European Higher Education Institutions Recognise Student Engagement. European STEP Survey Report* www.asso.li/stepsurveyreport

A diversity of practices linked to policy framework

If the Bologna process tends to harmonise the European higher education system, **each country and HEI still have their specificities**. All of them can count students engaged in non-academic activities among their ranks, but the issue of recognition is not always addressed the same way. The diversity of student engagement fields mirrors the diversity of forms of recognition. These differences can also be explained by the national context. Indeed, the first step of the project²⁴ revealed that European countries could be divided into three categories:

- Countries with a policy framework on the recognition of student engagement in non-profit activities, **for higher education in particular**.
- Countries with a policy framework on the recognition of engagement in non-profit activities **independent from higher education**.

- **Countries without any policy framework** on the recognition of engagement in non-profit activities.

Moreover, all HEIs do not recognise every extracurricular activity as an engagement. If there is a general trend to favour regular activities more than episodic ones, some universities only recognise engagement carried out in an association outside the university, others only in associations from the universities. Religious or political activities tend to be less recognised by European universities, except for political mandates as students' representatives which are sometimes the only activity recognised. Very seldom, we also found some universities for whom being engaged is a private matter and who believe it is not their role to promote or prevent it²⁵.

But most higher education institutions are more and more interested in this question and there is a wide range of schemes implemented in order to promote, value and validate it. Indeed, recognition of student engagement can take different forms: it can be through the facilitation of student life, the implementation of a diploma supplement detailing the skills of a student, a certificate of

²⁴ European Student Engagement Project (2019). Mapping of policy frameworks for student engagement recognition in Europe here: <https://www.animafac.net/minisite/european-step/european-step-en/>

²⁵ European Student Engagement Project (2020). *A Qualitative study: Crossed perspectives on student engagement and its recognition in European higher education institutions*: <https://www.animafac.net/media/O3-Report-English.pdf>

engagement or an award, a specific training, etc. Previous studies of the project showed that if most engaged students are not looking for recognition when they get engaged, they would nevertheless greatly appreciate it if their universities supported them in one way or another.

Thus, implementing practices known and appreciated by students would serve both to give legitimacy to students who are already engaged as well as an incentive for students who hesitate to get engaged or do not know how to do it.

Part III

Overview of practices on the recognition of student engagement

In this first part, **we will review the different practices used in HEIs across Europe.** The previous studies of European STEP outlined a wide range of practices used to recognise student engagement. **It is worth noting that there is no perfect scheme that would suit every student** and every HEIs because many other factors are to be taken into account when it comes to this issue such as cultural factors, what your goal when you recognise student engagement is, or what resources your institution is prepared to mobilise. **For each scheme presented, there will be a definition followed by an example of a HEI which has already implemented it.**

Formal recognition for the individual student, related to academic life

The formal recognition of student engagement related to academic life corresponds **to the integration of a student's engagement into his/her study programme.** This puts the engagement at the same level as other courses or modules and rewards it as one, via ECTS credits²⁶. However, there are different levels of integration into a study programme, and it can be considered as an extra course providing additional ECTS credits, as well as one where the ECTS credits are necessary to validate the degree prepared.

ECTS credits

One of the most used practices is the attribution of ECTS credits following a student's engagement. ECTS credits are a tool of the European Higher Education Area designed to allow students to have their qualifications recognised in any European institution:

²⁶ *European Credit Transfer and Accumulation system.* Website of the European Commission, more information here: https://ec.europa.eu/education/resources-and-tools/european-credit-transfer-and-accumulation-system-ects_en

“ECTS allows credits taken at one higher education institution to be counted towards a qualification studied for at another. ECTS credits represent learning based on defined learning outcomes and their associated workload”²⁷.

You need 30 ECTS credits to validate one semester, meaning that a bachelor’s degree represents 180 ECTS credits and a master’s degree 120.

A lot of universities have developed schemes to use this form of recognition. It can be recognised through the completion of an elective module, and sometimes be integrated as part of the curricula. If nothing of the sort exists in the university, it is worth checking the national legislation: in some countries, it is mandatory for HEIs to recognise student engagement. If there is indeed such legislation, you can claim additional ECTS credits to the academic or administrative staff depending on your country – for example in France it would be the headteacher of your programme of study – which will then be delivered after the writing of an activity report.

For example, at the University of Vienna in Austria, it is possible to have up to 15 ECTS credits recognised by carrying student representation activities. The amount of ECTS depends on their functions and duties in the Student Union. This recognition is administered by the student service center, but it is up to the study programme manager to give the final word on how many ECTS credits will be awarded.

At the University of Cantabria in Spain, students can be delivered a certificate of credits which is converted into ECTS credits once taken to the secretariat of the student’s department of study. For every 25 hours of volunteering, a student receives 1 ECTS credit.

However, when the ECTS credits obtained are just a small bonus – it is usually between 1 and 6 ECTS credits – but are not part of the ones needed to validate a degree, they are not always the option preferred by students. For some students it is appreciated as a sign that something is done to recognise their engagement.

²⁷ Definition of the European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu/education/resources-and-tools/european-credit-transfer-and-accumulation-system-ects_en

For some other students, if they have a choice, they would prefer alternatives, as explained by this member of the administrative staff at the Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw:

“It wasn't that popular form of recognition among students [...]. They could choose whether they wanted to receive a certificate of contribution, a certificate about internship or the ECTS. And the lowest number chose the recognition in the form of ECTS.”
Administrative staff member,
Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw, Poland

Elective module

The creation of an elective module in your university gives students **the opportunity to have their engagement being recognised through the completion of an academic module for non-academic activities**. To pass this module, students usually have to write a report on the activities carried out, or a reflective essay on what they learned during their involvement period. In some institutions, students also have to follow a training course on the notion of engagement or on the associative field. Like any other module at the university, it is rewarded with ECTS. Depending on your university and your programme of study, the ECTS credits

earned through this scheme can be either contributory or non-contributory, meaning that they can be integrated into the number of ECTS credits needed to validate your semester, or that they can be added to those required.

At the University of Cergy-Paris in France, students can subscribe to an elective module called “Student engagement” if they are part of an association in or outside the university. During their engagement period, they have to write a report which will be assessed by a board including members of the university and a member of the association that received the volunteer. Moreover, students have to follow a training course on associative engagement to have a broader understanding of what is at stake in the fields of solidarity and associative work. The successful applicants will be rewarded with 3 ECTS credits. To help students find a structure to get involved in, the University has developed partnerships with three associations in the field of education (AFEV, Expli'cité, ZUPdeCO).

One other interesting use of this mechanism is that it can allow the institution to choose structures they trust in which students will carry out their engagement.

For instance, the COMplementa tu FOrmación (COMFO) program of the University of Valladolid. Before their engagement begins, students have to attend up to 10 hours of presentation by different associations and then choose in which one they want to work. The program puts an emphasis on social and environmental associations, as well as on the values associated with these fields.

"It completes the professional curriculum by adding training on values and the existing social fabric. Its aim is to cross a work experience with an ethical reflection and a scale of values, thus generating cosmopolitan and socially committed citizens more capable of improving the environment in which they live cooperatively."²⁸

Elective module integrated as part of the curricula

²⁸ OMFO. Website of the Volunteer Association of the University of Valladolid: <https://voluntariado.uva.es/comfo/>

Some universities decided to integrate student engagement as part of one or several programmes of study. In this case, students have to complete the activity to have the number of ECTS credits required. As seen previously, an elective module can sometimes be integrated as part of the curricula, but it can sometimes be mandatory where the studies followed lead to a career path in associations, social work or project management. Student engagement can also be integrated as part of the curricula across the institution, meaning that it is available to all students independently from their programme of study.

The Office of Student Life of Dublin City University in Ireland has developed the Uaneen Module²⁹ which can be taken by any final year student on undergraduate or postgraduate programmes. Moreover, it can even be contributory depending on your programme of study. This means that it is taken into account as a module needed to pass your degree, and the portfolio realised to reflect upon your engagement replaces the usual end of degree dissertation. Approximately 125 hours of work are needed to complete this module and get 5 ECTS, and the assessment is based on a portfolio submitted by the students. The Uaneen Module is also endorsed by

²⁹ Uaneen Module. Website of Dublin City University: <https://www.dcu.ie/uaneen/testimonials-uaneen-module>

the Irish Business and Employers Confederation which is the largest business lobby group in Ireland because ***the skills acquired through student engagement are valued by employers.*** Moreover, students who take this module really appreciate the opportunity to reflect upon their engagement, to take the time to think about what they accomplished and analyse what they learnt.

“My favourite aspect of the Uaneen module was the opportunity to reflect on how I had grown during my time at DCU as I wrote my portfolio during my final year. It was extremely satisfying to collect my memories and see how my extra-curricular activities enabled me to develop a host of valuable skills.”³⁰

Student who followed the Uaneen Module
Dublin City University, Ireland

At Mykolas Romeris University in Lithuania, students can choose to ask for an individual study plan which allows them to free some time if they wish to carry out an engagement. However, this measure is not especially turned toward engagement but is more a recognition of the fact that students have other obligations and can carry out other activities alongside their studies.

³⁰Uaneen Module. Website of Dublin City University:
<https://www.dcu.ie/uaneen/testimonials-uaneen-module>

into account and aims at facilitating students’ academic life, by offering them more flexibility in their schedules or by giving them a little bonus in their grades.

Scheduling of school hours

Letting students choose their own timetable or skip some classes when it is justified is greatly appreciated by them even if it means they have to study more at home to catch up with the missing lectures. However, this form of valorisation of student engagement is rarely implemented as such in universities and is more often the result of an informal agreement between engaged students and their teachers.

“In Lithuania in general each of the students, for one or another reason, are being engaged in the university, outside of the university, or for personal reasons they can ask for individual learning plans anyway.”

Administrative staff member

Mykolas Romeris University, Lithuania.

Specific status for engaged students

Another way for students to adapt their timetable is to create a specific status for engaged students. A specific status usually applies to elected students' representatives, students who carry a mandate in an association, or professional athletes or artists. This status allows students not to follow every class where it is justified and to be sometimes exempted from classes. It can also give students more benefits to help them balance their associative engagement with their studies. In France, this status was registered in the National plan of student life in 2015 after the French network of student associations, Animafac, advocated for it. The implementation of this status was then experimented in different universities, such as the University of Clermont-Auvergne and the University of Sorbonne-Nouvelle which have kept it ever since.

At the University of Clermont-Auvergne in France, there are different specific statuses for students: for artists, for sportsmen and sportswomen, for volunteer firefighters and for students who hold responsibilities in associations. Having one of this status can give you access to various rights: a registration in the diploma supplement mentioning the status, the associative engagement and the skills acquired, an access to training on the identification and development of skills, as well as a punctual authorisation to be absent.

This status also offers the possibility to validate the associative experience as an internship if it is close to your field of study, and to validate a free module on student engagement. In return, students who benefit from this status have to follow at least two trainings offered by the Direction of student life and provide a reflexive analysis on the skills acquired during their engagement. What is interesting is not the status in itself but the rights associated with it which vary depending on the institution's expectations of student engagement.

“This status enables students to promote an associative engagement in their program of study, in particular by highlighting the acquired skills.”³¹

Website of the University of Clermont-Auvergne, France

bonus points awarded does not depend on the activity carried out, but on the way the activity is presented. An emphasis is put on the skills that may have been acquired during the engagement.

Extra-points

A student can gain extra-points on his/her average semester grades. These points can be earned after the completion of an elective module, or after validation by an evaluation committee. The number of points rarely exceeds 0,5 points on their average mark and cannot be used to pass a semester that would not be validated without it. However, it can help students graduate with honours.

At the University of Paris-Dauphine in France, students who volunteer in an association or who are elected as representatives gain from 0,1 to 0,4 point in their average mark. In order to benefit from this bonus, students have to present an activity report to a board including the vice president of the “Commission de la Formation et de la Vie Étudiante” (Training and Student Life Commission), the director of the department of study, and an external evaluator. The number of

³¹ Specific status for students who hold responsibilities in a non-profit organisation, in French : *Statut d'étudiant responsable associatif*. Website of the University of Clermont-

Auvergne: <https://www.uca.fr/campus/statuts-specifiques-detudiant/responsable-associatif>

Recognition in the form of non-academic awards for students and as a community building tool

These forms of recognition are not academic ones but **aim at promoting student engagement and the values it may carry**. By giving space to student associations and putting in the spotlight students and their engagement, institutions seek to energise campus life, bring a sense of community and boost the number of engaged students.

Valorisation and promotion of student engagement

This practice is more a set of practices which represents everything that is done by an HEI to enhance student engagement. It can be achieved **through the dedication of space for students' association, the possibility to set up events, or institutional communication on students' associations and projects**. These practices can help as a community-building tool.

The University of Warsaw in Poland provides this kind of valorisation of student engagement through the Volunteer Centre. This administrative department of the University conducts several missions such as the recruitment of volunteers, the promotion of volunteering and the highlighting of students' projects. Students can go there with their ideas of projects and get some assistance to develop and implement them, often in cooperation with an NGO. They can participate in workshops and training on the topic of project management or in the field of self-development, all connected to the types of activities volunteers are involved in. This is also a place of exchange, to meet other volunteers and to develop a network.

“Between 2014 and 2018, the number of volunteers at the Volunteer Centre increased from 288 to 1354”³²

³² About the Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw:
<https://wolontariat.uw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/ENG-plansza-1-poprawki.pdf>

Certificate of engagement

A certificate of engagement can be delivered for committed students as **a proof of their participation in an extra-curricular activity**. It consists of a more or less detailed document delivered by the university or the hosting association regarding the activity carried out. Sometimes a simple proof of participation, a certificate can also detail the activities carried out during the engagement and for some institutions, it is also a document where the skills acquired during the engagement are listed. A certificate can be issued directly by the institution, but can also be delivered by the structure where the engagement took place and then validated by the institution.

The Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw also offers different kinds of certificates. They used to offer students a choice between ECTS credits and a certificate in one of the projects. However, since the vast majority of students asked for the certificate, the Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw did not continue the recognition in the form of ECTS. Based on this example, we can see that offering students a choice on how they prefer their engagement to be recognised is in itself a good practice to assess which practices are the most valued from the perspectives of students.

“Indeed students are collecting such certificates very carefully as proofs of their engagements”

Staff member

The Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw, Poland

At the University of Cantabria in Spain, students can be delivered a certificate detailing the skills acquired by the student. The information is given by the structure in which the engagement was carried out and then transferred to the university which turns it into a certificate of skills. In this case, the focus is on the acquired skills in order to facilitate the entry on the labour market.

Award

An award is close to a certificate but **it is seen as a distinction rather than a proof of participation**. Sometimes, the award can be delivered during a ceremony, thus putting committed students and student engagement in the spotlight.

Dublin City University in Ireland offers different levels of awards and one of these - The Uaneen Module- is celebrated during a special ceremony, which takes place on the same day as the student's graduation, but at a different time and in a separate location to distinguish it from the academic ceremony.

Each year between 50- 70 students are celebrated in this way. The Award is presented by the President or Deputy President of the University. Sometimes there may be a guest, for example, a sportsperson who has graduated from the DCU programme or a graduate from the media.

They would typically have a strong connection with DCU and may also be a graduate of the Uaneen Module. This is a special occasion and a worthwhile practice as it formally and publicly

recognises students who have volunteered or given their time to community or sporting organisations. They, and their families, get to meet the University President or Deputy in an informal setting. They are photographed and the ceremony is publicised on the DCU website. It is a fitting way for these engagement students to mark the end of not only their academic journey but also their extracurricular one.

Recognition of the skills acquired through engagement activities

Carrying out an engagement means being confronted with other environments than the academic one, **which helps students develop new skills that will be useful in their professional and individual life**. Employers are increasingly paying attention to transversal skills and their recognition is encouraged by the European Union³³. Recognising skills is a way to give a more complete overview of one person's abilities on top of their qualifications.

“Qualifications signal to employers what people know and are able to do but rarely capture skills acquired outside formal learning institutions, which therefore risk being undervalued”³⁴

European Commission

Validation of the skills acquired through the experience of engagement

This scheme is focused on the skills acquired. It can be “hard” skills such as project management, accountancy or digital skills, but also “soft” skills that are more and more valued as team working, leadership, self-confidence or empathy.

The acquired skills can be evaluated by the institution directly through an evaluation committee, but can also be assessed by the organisation where the engagement took place and then validated by the institution.

The University of Aix-Marseille in France recognises student engagement through a “validation device of student engagement”. For students who have responsibilities in an association external to the university or who volunteer with the firefighters, it is possible to be exempted from some classes and from the internship if the skills acquired through the engagement are similar to the ones taught in the degree.

³³ *European skills agenda*. <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1223&langId=en>

³⁴ *COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF*

THE REGIONS A NEW SKILLS AGENDA FOR EUROPE. European Commission, 10/06/2016: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0381&from=EN>

To benefit from this device, the applicant must submit a report to a jury who will examine it and decide whether or not the skills are validated. The report, of approximately 2000 words, consists of a description of the activities accomplished and a self-evaluation of the skills acquired. If the skills do not match the ones demanded by the degree, the jury can also decide to reward the student with extra ECTS credits. The skills and learnings identified by the jury are valued by an entry in the diploma supplement.

Diploma supplement

This tool was set up at the instigation of the European Commission as part of the Bologna process, the aim of which is to harmonise higher education systems in Europe. **The diploma supplement gives details about one's diploma, qualifications, results and can also provide additional information.** In the latter part, reference may be made to extra-curricular activities. Sometimes it is a description of the activities carried out, to which can be added details about the skills acquired and at what level. If the diploma supplement is supposed to be granted by all higher education

institutions, reference to extra-curricular activities is not mandatory for the university.

The University of Coimbra in Portugal issues the diploma supplement to each student receiving his/her diploma. All activities that can be registered on the diploma supplement are clearly listed on its website³⁵. Some extracurricular activities are directly added to the supplement without students having to ask for it, such as being a student representative or participating in cultural activities inside the university. Other activities such as tutoring other students or carrying out a civic voluntary service can be added at the request of the students.

Digital badges

Digital badges are an innovative way to recognise informal learning. **They are indicators of qualifications or skills acquired in different learning environments and are being implemented in several universities across Europe.** Students can acquire different

³⁵ *Diploma Supplement*. Website of the University of Coimbra:
<https://www.uc.pt/en/academicos/documentos/suplemento/>

badges for different skills acquired or activities carried out, and these badges are then available online for possible employers.

The University of Tours in France tested the “engagement Open Badges” during the academic year 2018-2019, for engaged students, volunteers, army reservists, or volunteer firefighters. One badge corresponds to one competence acquired during the experience of engagement of a student. Students can collect different badges online associated with their engagement skills.

To get a badge, they have to fill a form in which they explain how their engagement is related to one or several skills. During the experiment, the University provided 18 kind of badges related to engagement, and students could contact the office of student life if they identified other skills they acquired. To develop this technology, university staff and students worked together to elaborate which criteria were required to obtain a badge.

“The open badge allows you to formalise the informal, to show that when you have a voluntary experience you learn skills and knowledge that are a little different”

Academic staff member
University of Tours, France

Training sessions for engaged students

Universities can organise workshops or conferences to help would-be volunteers. These can be managed by university staff or teachers together with professionals. The training sessions can introduce students to the associative world revolving about environmental or social issues, prepare them to project management and how to operate an association, or offer them the possibility to reflect upon their engagement and the skills they acquire in their extra-curricular activities. This approach is interesting because it gives a clear role to the HEI which is to give theoretical as well as reflexive approaches on student engagement.

The Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw in Poland provides different workshops and training sessions to accompany engaged students in their activity. These training sessions help students face difficulties during their engagement and also offers them the possibility to identify what they learnt and how to valorise it.

Financial support

“There are workshops and training specific on the topic of project management and ideas development. Whenever we have a possibility, we organise workshops in the field of general self-development. Often it concerns soft-skills training, connected with the types of activities that students are involved in when they volunteer – so they could evolve. It’s about being creative but also often these are general-development activities and just spending nice time together, in community.”

Staff member

The Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw, Poland

It can be argued that student engagement should not be rewarded with money lest we lose the “spirit” of engagement. However, **providing financial support can be a way to give students the means to develop a project**, as well as to allow the ones who do not have stable financial resources to get engaged for the community instead of having to find a job.

Financial support for student-led projects

Funding student projects is a way to give space to innovation coming directly from the students and to value initiative and entrepreneurship.

The University College of Ghent in Belgium created the “ENGAGE: Small things matter” fund which helps fund students’ projects up to 500€. After a presentation in front of a jury, 10 projects are selected to be funded. From a boarding school for deaf students in Nepal to homework help for pupils in disadvantaged

neighbourhoods³⁶, different kinds of projects are selected that tackle issues in the fields of education, culture, international solidarity or the environment. The ENGAGE fund is financed partly through activities organised by the Student Council which is also a member of the jury who chooses the projects.

In some countries, this kind of funds exists at a national scale. In France, a national fund devoted to student initiatives has existed since 2001. To finance it, a certain amount is deducted from the tuition fees of each student every year.

“In particular, student projects are one of the most visible forms of associative commitment. They are an opportunity for students to express a variety of talents but also to acquire skills that enrich their academic career and contribute to their future professional and social success.”³⁷

French Ministry of higher education, research and innovation

³⁶ Those are two projects selected in the “ENGAGE: Small things matter” programme in 2020

A criterion when applying for a scholarship

Being an engaged student is certainly a bonus on your resume, and it is also valued by some universities which take it into consideration during the application for a scholarship. Indeed, **it is sometimes a valued criterion for students who need help to finance their studies.**

The University of Public Service in Budapest, Hungary, offers a scholarship for public affairs to every student who is engaged in the Student Union. The head of the Student Union is responsible for the paperwork and documentation related to the granting of the scholarship and is supervised by the Vice-Rector for Educational Affairs.

“So basically we were, this is something like I would not say a company but I would say, some kind of a public institution. Which means, that we are overseen by officials and we are able to pay for our people who are serving“.

Student and former president of the student government of
University of Public Service of Budapest, Hungary

³⁷ P. Hetzel for the ministry of higher education, research and innovation, *Bulletin officiel n° 43 du 24 novembre 2011*. https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/pid20536/bulletin-officiel.html?cid_bo=58373&cbo=1

Scholarships for engaged students can also be granted by other institutions than HEIs. The city of Warsaw has a scholarship programme managed by the Centre for the Thought of John Paul II. The Centre funds over 600 pupils and students each year for a total amount of nearly PLN 2.5 millions (approximately 560 000 euros). Students who are engaged in social matters, have good grades and a low family income can receive this scholarship.

A combination of practices for a better recognition

In the first part of this guidebook, we focused on one or two mechanisms of student engagement recognition per HEIs. But most of them have developed several other practices regarding this issue. Since there is no perfect formula transferable to all universities when it comes to student engagement recognition, each HEI is free to implement schemes that suit them the best based on what they expect from student engagement and what the students need. Indeed, some schemes are especially designed to promote student engagement while others focus on increasing the employability of its students or on reinforcing a sense of community in the institution.

Thus, **a lot of HEIs use a combination of different schemes for different purposes.** Having different ways of recognising student engagement is also a way to answer students' needs on this issue, and to assess if some practices are better than others.

In the **first annex** you can find a recap table of the HEIs cited in this guidebook designed to give a more general overview of the combination of practices that can be implemented in one institution.

Part IV

Advocating for student engagement recognition

There are many ways to understand student engagement, and just as many ways to recognise it. **Implementing practices of recognition of student engagement requires time and dedication** to have an efficient system as well as to meet the expectations of the different stakeholders involved on the issue in the institution. The previous studies led as part of the European Student Engagement Project (European STEP), revealed that there are many different perceptions on the issue of the recognition of student engagement and that engaged students are not always aware of what exists in their institution.

To have an efficient and appreciated system of recognition, **it is important to involve as many members at the start of the institutions as possible**, meaning not only members of the staff but

importantly students who are not to be forgotten as they will be the main beneficiaries of this system. It may not be possible and even not efficient to involve too many people during the whole process of the elaboration of this system, but the key concept of carrying on a project to recognise student engagement remains **co-construction**³⁸.

Moreover, it is important **to communicate** on the advancement of the project at institutional level to attract the attention and the support of students and other members of the institution. This process of elaboration is to be carried out over several months, sometimes years.

One must note that recognition of student engagement is still an under-researched field of study. The EXTRAsup European project³⁹, that was initially designed to find the best practices to recognise student engagement and extracurricular activities in general, quickly established **that there was no perfect formula transferable to all higher education institutions**.

³⁸More on the Co-construction Method: <http://responsibility-navigator.eu/co-construction-method/#anchor-0-0>

³⁹ EXTRAsup is an European Project on extracurricular activities. It results in a kit especially designed to help bring about changes in higher education institutions by recognising extracurricular activities. To read more: <http://www.extrasup.eu/>

What we offer here are only **suggestions** of thought and action to try and improve the situation of student engagement recognition based on the studies led during the European STEP project. Thus, we are proposing a method to assess what changes are required or requested in your institution, and how to bring about those changes. For that, you will have different supporting documents and an example of an experimentation led in France in 2014. However, there is still plenty of scope for innovation and ideas to make it work better.

A four-step guide to advocate for recognition of student engagement

As mentioned above, what we propose here is only one way to advocate for recognition of student engagement. **We propose a process in four steps to help you advocate for recognition of student engagement.**

- The first one consists of reviewing how the issue is dealt within your institution and gathering a motivated team.
- The second step focuses on elaborating an action plan for recognising student engagement in your institution.
- The third step is to elaborate the argument and the strategy of dissemination.
- And finally, the last step is to launch an experimentation.

First step

Reviewing how the issue is dealt within your HEI and gathering a motivated team

The first step consists in acquiring a general picture of how the issue of student engagement and its recognition is dealt within your institution and in gathering a motivated team to advocate for the changes you want to carry out.

Objectives:

- Gathering data on which practices exist in your institution;**
- Identifying the changes required or requested in your institution;**
- Gathering a team of motivated students and members of the teaching, academic and administrative staff.**

Gathering data on which practices exist in your institution

In order to help you gather data on which practices exist in your institution, we propose you complete a **self-diagnosis exercise**.

The self-diagnosis tools proposed, if possible, are to be tested with as many people as possible. It is best to organise a collective session dedicated to student engagement recognition at the University, but these tables can also be filled individually.

- **If you are a student or a group of students**, you can fill in the self-diagnosis table on the schemes available in your institution to recognise student engagement (Annex 2).
- **If you are a member of the university staff** (administrative member or academic) you can fill in the self-diagnosis table on the schemes available in your institution to recognise student engagement (Annex 3).

After completing the self-diagnosis you should now have a clearer picture of how the issue of recognition of student engagement is dealt within your institution and start thinking about how you may change it.

Identifying the changes required or requested in your institution

Launching a discussion

Once the tables are filled in, you can launch a discussion on the different results with your peers. After completing the self-diagnosis you may organise a larger discussion including students and staff members to compare the results and review the issue altogether. This discussion may reveal a discrepancy in access to information and difference of perceptions depending on the status of the person who completed it.

- If the tables were filled online individually: you can analyse the results and invite the participants who wish to participate further in the project to a discussion on the results of this first diagnosis.
- If the tables were filled during a face-to-face session: you can launch the discussion directly, and invite the most motivated members to participate in the next steps of the project.

In both cases, it is also useful during this discussion to introduce the other practices presented in the first part of the

guidebook so that the participants can decide whether or not they wish to implement a new practice in your institution.

Summing up your discussion

Thanks to the first diagnosis, you should have a clearer idea of the changes requested by the students and other members of the institution, and whether or not there is a demand to introduce new practices.

Here is **a list of questions** that may help you sum up what changes you want to carry out after having discussed with different members of the institution and analysed the results of this first diagnosis. **Answering these questions will give you a first idea of the general direction of the project.**

- **What are the practices already implemented in your institution?** *The reason behind the implementation of a practice of recognition of student engagement can determine the practice you wish to implement. Is it to increase the number of engaged students? To help students acquire new skills? To energise campus life?*

- **Are the students aware that these practices exist?**

- **Are the students generally satisfied with the current practices?**

- Is there a demand to introduce new practices in your institution? And if there is, which one(s)?

- **Did any obstacles emerge?** (e.g.: *members of the institutions completely opposed to the implementation of such measures*)

Gathering a team of motivated students and members of the teaching, academic and administrative staff

After answering the different questions and completing the tables designed to help you have a clearer idea of what you want and need to work on, you can look for new persons who would like to join your project. **Having a motivated and diverse team who will manage this project for a longer period is important to ensure that different points of view are represented.** One key to carry out a successful and sustainable project is co-construction.

To encourage students to engage in this matter, you can make them the first group of students who will benefit from the new measures of recognition at the end of the project. Also to reach staff members who might be interested in your project, do not hesitate to contact administrative staff members working on student engagement, cultural or sports issues. You can start with a group of 4-5 people.

The next steps will help you have a deeper knowledge of your institution's practices by analysing the different issues surrounding the recognition of student engagement.

Second step

Developing an action plan for recognising student engagement

This step consists in **acquiring deeper knowledge on how your institution works in terms of student engagement and its recognition** in order to define more precisely what you want to change. Now that you have a general overview of the issue and the differences that can exist between the students' and the university side. It is now the time to elaborate an action plan for recognising student engagement.

Objectives:

- Acquiring a deeper knowledge of how your institution recognises student engagement, if it does so;**
- Defining which modalities of recognition of student engagement to carry out.**

Acquiring a deeper knowledge of how your institution recognises student engagement

In order to help you, we propose you to complete **different tables**. They are designed to give more indications on who can benefit from this recognition, who is in charge of evaluating the engagement, and which types of engagement can be recognised. They can also serve as a basis of reflection by showing the different modalities of recognition.

These are more precise and sometimes more technical questions to be discussed with the team of students and members of the staff who agreed to participate further in the project. During this step, it is important to keep in mind why you wish to recognise student engagement as it can define what choices you will make. It is also important to define which body will be in charge of it: it is usually the Office of Student Life, but it can also be an association.

For this, **you can report to the tables in the (Annex 4)**. You can fill it with your team composed of students and university's staff members.

Defining which modalities of recognition of student engagement to carry out

In order to have concrete results at the end of a project, having a plan and set attainable objectives can help you. It may allow you to advance in the project on the basis of a set framework that will help you to clearly identify what you will do during the time of the project.

The table below is here to help you answer the five Ws and How (what, why, who, when, where and how).

- **Which practice do you wish to implement and why?** *Depending on the practice you wish to implement, more or less issues need to be addressed. For example, if the focus is on the skills acquired, how to assess the skills acquired? Is it done by the host organisation or by the institution? Is there a need for an external evaluator?...*

- **Who will be the beneficiaries of these practices?** *If it is best to have a small group test who will be the first beneficiaries of these new measures, you also need to set from the beginning if all students will at the end benefit from it, or if it is directed only to final year students or only for students in some programmes of study.*

- **What is the planned duration of the project?** *Bringing about change in an institution is a long process and all issues need to be addressed for a successful experiment. Before launching the first experiment, it is better to have developed the project for at least a semester, probably a full year. Having a deadline from the beginning of the project will help you organise your work accordingly.*

- **At what level will you first experiment the implementation of the practice?** *Knowing at what level (faculty, department, programme of study,..) you will first implement the recognition of student engagement allows you to target more specifically the public who will participate in the experiment and inform them early on about the project you carry out.*

- **What means will you use to carry out the project?** *The means needed to implement measures of recognition of student engagement may depend on your institution and the time and the amount of time members of the working group are able to allocate to the project. Will you need to build advocacy on the issue? How regularly will you meet to discuss the project? How will you communicate on the issue?*

Third step Advocacy and outreach

This part is designed to help you build an advocacy on student engagement depending on the level of student engagement recognition in your institution outlined by the first diagnosis and second diagnosis.

Objectives:

- ❑ **Building advocacy for recognition of student engagement;**
- ❑ **Raising awareness among the relevant stakeholders.**

For this step, **you will find some different approaches you can use depending on the results of the diagnosis.** We also outlined from the previous studies the different reasons given by the institutions regarding the obstacles to the implementation of such measures, and we added possible arguments to respond to those reasons. You will also find **more general guidelines to prepare an advocacy on student engagement recognition.**

So, first, here are some scenarios that can help you before building your advocacy depending on the results of the previous diagnosis.

Scenario 1: There is no recognition of student engagement in any form whatsoever

- If there is nothing done to recognise student engagement, it is important to find out why. We have listed some of the recurrent arguments given by the universities on the lack of such measures, and some arguments you can oppose.
- At first, it can be smart to propose schemes that do not require too much change in the institution such as the inscription of the extracurricular activities carried out in the diploma supplement, or ask for a place to be made available for associations.
- You can offer to set up a students' association that will help the process by offering opportunities for engagement, establishing partnerships, organising an award ceremony, etc.
- You may also ask for support already existing e.g. from active student associations or organisations that are already established in your institution to use their resources.

Scenario 2: Some schemes are being implemented but are not well developed or irrelevant

- An assessment of student engagement recognition practices may have been carried out, you can ask the office responsible for student life. It is useful to consult it to try and see what are the successes and the obstacle points.
- Even if you do not find the practices relevant, the process of recognising student engagement has already begun which means that you should find people who will support your approach. It can then be useful to find who are the people at the origin of the process and who is responsible for implementing it. Avoid going to them only to criticise the practices but try to present solutions or different options to improve them.

Scenario 3: There are some well-developed practices but they are only available to a small part of the students/institution

- An assessment of student engagement recognition practices may have been carried out. If such documents exist, it is important to draw information from them and see what was successful in the implementation of the practices and how the issue was approached.
- Try and find results, testimonies, data showing that these practices have been beneficial for students.
- Find out who set it up in the institution and try to have their support for implementing it for your department, faculty, or the whole institution.

Scenario 4: The university communicates a lot on its missions to help students have a successful life as professionals and citizens, but the practices on student engagement recognition are lacking.

- Try and find how you can use the communication campaign of the university to build your case.
- Check the institution's strategic plan. They often set objectives such as: "we will prepare [our students] well to flourish in the world outside the university: in their personal lives, in civic society, and in the rapidly evolving workplace" (DCU) or "strengthen the ability to transform the local area, social situation and the environment towards sustainable economic development and an inclusive social model." (University of Health of Barcelona). It can play in your favour if your approach is part of a bigger strategy of the institution, for instance if your institution considers that it has a third mission.
- If the communication is the only problem, you can also offer to help in organising a campaign or an event to inform other students from your institution. You can do this by organising yourself with other members of student associations.

Building advocacy for recognition of student engagement

Clarifying the key concepts

For the process of student engagement recognition to work efficiently, it is important to clarify the different concepts needed so you and the different stakeholders in the process will be on the same page regarding the words used⁴⁰. The key concepts to define generally are: recognise (identify, name, acknowledge, accept...); value; validate; extracurricular activities (what does it include?); engagement (what activities does it refer to?); learning outcomes; skills; competences.

Identifying the stakeholders

There are key members in the institution who need to be informed of the advancement of the project for efficiency and communication purposes.

The Office of Student Life is often in charge of this issue and even if it is not, it is best to be in contact with the people who work

⁴⁰ See more on the method proposed by EXTRAsup: <http://www.extrasup.eu/>

there so that they can inform students about engagement recognition.

You may also present your work and inform students who manage associations in your university because they will at some point benefit from these measures. Moreover, they can inform their network about it and be a useful group of support. The elected student representatives and the VP can be strategic allies on this issue as well, especially when advocating for recognition to different bodies in the institution.

There are of course more members of the institution who need to agree upon the project and be kept informed of its advancement, such as teachers and governing bodies.

If your recognition practices include external partners, it is also best to contact them as soon as possible to see what role they will have in the process of recognition of student engagement.

Elaborating the argument for recognition

The first step to prepare advocacy is to clarify the issue of student engagement recognition and the problems with the existing system if there are some. The advocacy will consist of explaining why student engagement recognition is an improvement for the institution and its students. You can give several reasons: to empower students as

future citizens and professionals by strengthening academic background with the recognition of the experience of engagement or the skills acquired, to help them develop soft skills, to increase the number of engaged students, to facilitate their integration to the labour market, to revitalise the university campus and student life, etc. To help you define the argument, we propose a series of arguments and counter-arguments that can inspire you in besides.

Main reasons given by members of HEI about the obstacles of implementing such measures and possible counter arguments

- **"Lack of resources"**: Not all practices require huge resources and changes in the institution, so you can ask for a small act of recognition. For example, the diploma supplement is already supposed to be delivered to each student who asks for it. The aim of the diploma supplement is to give a clearer idea to future employers of the qualifications and the skills acquired during your studies. You can therefore propose that it mentions the missions and the tasks carried out during an engagement, maybe even the skills acquired. Same goes for a certificate of engagement that could be delivered by the host structure and stamped by your university, or directly by the university. It would help legitimise students' engagements.

➤ **"Students "are not interested" or "don't have time" to carry on an engagement experience"**: To this argument, you are the best proof that yes, "students are interested", that you managed to find some time to carry out your engagement aside from your studies, and that it has brought you skills that could not be acquired in a pure academic context.

➤ **"Fear of losing the "real" spirit of engagement"**: The reasons underlying this argument are fears that engagement becomes mandatory, maybe even discriminatory to students who do not get engaged. If those are legitimate concerns, this is not a necessary component of student engagement recognition. The effectiveness of recognition depends on this fine balance: higher education institutions are expected to facilitate, encourage and recognise engagement, but not to impose a binding framework or to set specific expectations and objectives that would go against the very notion of engagement. The positive aspect of recognition is about making students feel they are more legitimate to engage.

➤ **"Too many possibilities"**: If this argument is given, it probably means that the schemes implemented or the absence of scheme resulted in poor consultations between the stakeholders. In this case, it would be interesting to set up a meeting with the different stakeholders in order to consider the different options and see which practices would make consensus between the different stakeholders. To this purpose, you can use this guide of good practices and the previous studies of the European STEP project to present the different opportunities.

➤ **The institution is too rigid" or "the institution only does it to comply with the law" or "there is no centralised strategy/policy"**: These reasons may be given by members of the support or academic staff but that does not mean they will not support you if you try to build a case to have student engagement recognised. In any way, the best way is to include the different stakeholders to co-construct the project.

Defining the objectives and the modalities

After the previous working sessions, you should now be able to identify and determine the propositions you want to carry out. But also you need to define the modalities, the stakeholders and the steps you need to follow to launch your experimentation.

Then, this advocacy should clearly identify the objectives and the way to achieve them. For this you need to mention which schemes you wish to improve or implement. It is important to remain realistic: propose to implement it at a reduced scale first. At first, it can be implemented at the department or the faculty level, or even for one programme of study.

Defining the audience and the advantages

You should also determine the audience that will benefit from your proposition and what the exact advantages will be.

Raising awareness among the relevant stakeholders

Gathering support

You may find **allies** among student associations, staff and teachers who will support your advocacy. You can also reach to associations or non-governmental organisations to see if they would be interested to participate in an engagement programme developed by the institution. You also may find at which steps you will contribute as a student to help co-construct this project in your institution (evaluation, communication, partnerships...).

Be also aware that it is also important to communicate on the advancement of the project to include a huge range of people and raise the interest of the community on the issue.

Fourth step Conducting an experiment

Objectives:

- Launching an experiment at a reduced scale;**
- Building a system of evaluation of the practice.**

Launching an experiment at a reduced scale

Once every modality of recognition is defined, **you can launch a first experiment** of this practice at the beginning of a semester. It is helpful to use a project methodology to implement the experiment.

For example, define at what level the experiment will be led (department, faculty, module) and which schemes will be implemented to recognise student engagement. Indeed, it is important to see if it works at a reduced scale, at the level of a programme of study or a small faculty. You can also decide to test your proposition with a few students. Then can, for example, be selected by your group and some members of the university and thus,

be a representative sample of the students that will be concerned by your proposition.

You may also define what will be recognised and how. Pay attention to the possible overlap between competencies acquired during courses and the skills acquired during the experience of engagement; ask yourselves what to do about it.

Try and have a thorough approach; it should be formalised, well documented and usable. The different stakeholders' roles have to be clear and the status of extracurricular skills in the curricula must be understood and recognised by all.

At this point, it is important to **have an evaluation system** to see during the experiment and at the end if it was successful. This process of evaluation is to be used for the following experiments to improve the system of recognition in your institution, and to ensure its sustainability.

Building a system of evaluation of the practice

To assess the result of a project and ameliorate its outcomes in the future, you can elaborate an evaluation process. **The purpose of its evaluation is to identify what worked best and what needs to be improved.** You have to be able to draw conclusions from the experiments to assess the acceptability of the project.

Try and think in terms of sustainability when it comes to change and organisation. You can, for example, use qualitative or quantitative indicators.

Qualitative indicators

- Satisfaction of the students: at the end of the experiment, you can ask the students who benefitted from it to answer a questionnaire of satisfaction with a few questions such as: did the recognition match your expectations? Is the workload of the engagement and the amount of recognition well-balanced? Was the workload needed to receive your recognition appropriate and useful (in case of a reflexive essay or a portfolio)?
- Satisfaction of external organisations (if any): are they satisfied with the work provided by the students they receive

in their organisation? Would they agree to continue the partnership for a longer period?

- Satisfaction of the members in charge of the recognition process: for these stakeholders, it is worth having a meeting and review with them the different steps of the project until then.

Quantitative indicators

- How many students benefited from the recognition measures?
- How much did it cost?

 Focus on an example in France

Specific Status for students who hold responsibilities in associations

Presentation of the status:

- **What:** this specific status was inspired by the status of high-level athletes. It confers a special and derogatory status for students who have responsibilities in student organisations.
- **By whom:** It has been carried out by Animafac, a network of student organisations in order to recognise student engagement, to help them reconcile studies and student engagement.
- **For who:** for students who have important responsibilities in non-profit organisations and would like to assume them without being prejudiced in their studies.
- **Why:** to entice students to engage, to recognise that engaged students are major actors in Student Life, to prove that non formal and formal education are compatible.

- **Advantages of the status:** allowing engaged students to study and be engaged at the same time:
 - the possibility to have an exemption of mid-term exams;
 - the possibility to validate the engagement as an internship when coherent with the field of studies;
 - the possibility to validate the experience of student engagement as a teaching unit.

Implementation and experimentation process:

- **When:** from 2014¹ to 2017
- **Where:** The experiment started within one university: the University of Sorbonne-Nouvelle, in Paris, France.
- **How:** a partnership agreement for the status of “Responsible for an organisation” between Animafac and the University of Sorbonne-Nouvelle was negotiated with the Vice-President of the Commission for Academic and University life.

- **Experimented by:** students engaged from different levels of studies and different fields who applied. They needed to submit an application form with information about the association (statutes, board members, budget, activities, financial report) and a cover letter mentioning their missions and the numbers of hours dedicated to them.
- **Selection process:** the applications were evaluated by a commission composed by the Vice-President of Academic Life, the directors of the University's life services, members of the Maison de la vie étudiante, Student Vice-president, a member of Animafac.
- **Who was in charge of following-up the experiment:** Student Office Life was appointed to receive the application forms and to manage the communication around the experimentation addressed to students and staff members and teachers and to follow and support the students concerned by the status.
- **How long:** one year experiment.

➤ **Incomes:**

- at a local level: In 2015-2016, the status was reconducted in the University of Sorbonne-Nouvelle, with 15 students who benefit from it, and more universities experimented the status, for example the University Blaise Pascal in Clermont-Ferrand¹;
 - at a national level: it allows an advocacy at a national scale, in 2016, that resulted in a national law: Equality and Citizenship Law in 2017, that obliges HEIs to recognise student engagement.
- ⇒ See more on Animafac's website:
www.animafac.net

Roadmap

Finally, after all the work done before you may be able to complete this roadmap in order to sum up your advocacy.

Modalities of recognition you want to implement:

.....

.....

.....

Arguments in favour of this recognition (examples to illustrate if relevant), what is at stake, what is the context:

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Conditions to benefit from it (if there are some):

-
-
-
-

Advantages conferred by this recognition:

-
-
-
-
-
-

Students concerned:

-
-

-
-

Modalities of implementation:

-
-
-
-
-
-

Conclusion

We hope that this guidebook helped you have a better understanding and knowledge about the recognition of student engagement in Europe and that it enticed you initiating changes in your institution.

Further activities of European STEP will aim to develop tools to support both students and institutions in this recognition process: an “engagement and skills” platform, a training kit adapted for each audience. It will also involve advocacy with public authorities to promote engagement and its recognition through a booklet of recommendations.

Sources

EUROPEAN STEP'S RESOURCES:

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2. European Student Engagement Project (2019). Mapping of legislative frameworks: www.animafac.net/minisite/european-step/european-step-en/
3. European Student Engagement Project (2019). How European Higher Education Institutions Recognise Student Engagement. European STEP Survey Report: www.asso.li/stepsurveyreport
4. European Student Engagement Project (2020). European STEP's qualitative study: Study on student engagement, its recognition, its perception and its effects among European Higher Education Institutions and students

EUROPEAN SOURCES:

5. European project ExtraSUP: <http://www.extrasup.eu/>
6. European Credit Transfer and Accumulation system. Website of the European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu/education/resources-and-tools/european-credit-transfer-and-accumulation-system-ects_en
7. European skills agenda: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1223&langId=en>
8. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A NEW SKILLS AGENDA FOR EUROPE. European Commission, 10/06/2016: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0381&from=EN>

HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS' WEBSITES:

1. "ENGAGE: Small things matter" fund at the University College of Ghent, Belgium: <https://www.hogent.be/fondsengage/project-indienen/>
2. Valorisation of student engagement at the University of Cergy-Pontoise, France: <https://www.u-cergy.fr/fr/vie-etudiante/vie-associative/valorisation-de-l-engagement-etudiant.html>
3. Specific status for engaged students at the University of Clermont-Auvergne, France: <https://www.uca.fr/campus/statuts-specifiques-d-etudiant/responsable-associatif/statut-d-etudiant-responsable-associatif-18477.kjsp>
4. Bonus points for engaged students at the University of Paris-Dauphine, France: <https://unidauphine.eu/actualites/engagement-etudiant/>
5. Validation device of the University of Aix-Marseille, France: <https://www.univ-amu.fr/fr/public/engagement-etudiant>
6. Experiment of the specific status for students who hold responsibilities in associations:
 - a. <https://www.animafac.net/actualites/animafac-sorbonne-nouvelle-experimentent-statut-responsable-associatif-etudiant/>

- b. <https://www.animafac.net/actualites/statut-responsable-associatif-arrive-clermont-ferrand/>
 - c. <https://www.animafac.net/actualites/statut-responsable-associatif-etudiant-bilan-positif-paris-3/>
 - d. <https://www.animafac.net/actualites/creation-dun-statut-responsable-associatif-etudiant/>
7. Open Badge at the University of Tours, France:
<https://openbadge.univ-tours.fr/>
 8. Diploma Supplement. Website of the University of Coimbra, Spain:
<https://www.uc.pt/en/academicos/documentos/suplemento/>
 9. COMFO program at the University of Valladolid, Spain:
<https://voluntariado.uva.es/comfo/>
 10. Uaneen module at Dublin City University, Ireland:
<https://www.dcu.ie/uaneen/home-uaneen-module>
 11. Mykolas Romeris University, Greece:
<https://www.mruni.eu/en/>
 12. Volunteer Centre of the University of Warsaw, Poland:
<https://wolontariat.uw.edu.pl/volunteers/>

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<https://www.animafac.net/blog/fsdie-les-universites-les-associatifs-etudiants-en-parlent/>
14. P. Hetzel for the ministry of higher education, research and innovation, *Bulletin officiel n° 43 du 24 novembre 2011* :
https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/pid20536/bulletin-officiel.html?cid_bo=58373&cbo=1
15. Claire Thoury, *Student engagement in a world of individualisation: identity construction and political careers.*, Sociology. Université Sorbonne Paris Cité, 2017, France.

Examples of HEI's practices

Category 1:	Category 2:	Category 3:
<i>Policy framework on the recognition of student engagement in non-profit activities, for higher education in particular.</i>	<i>Other policy framework on the recognition of engagement in non-profit activities independent from higher education.</i>	<i>No policy framework on the recognition of engagement in non-profit activities.</i>

Practices / Universities	University of Warsaw (Poland)	Vienna University (Austria)	Dublin City University (Ireland)	University of Cergy-Pontoise (France)	University of Clermont Auvergne (France)	University of Valladolid (Spain)	Paris-Dauphine University (France)	University of Tours (France)	University of Aix-Marseille (France)	University College Ghent (Belgium)	Charles University (Czech Republic)
Formal recognition for individual student, related to the academic life											
Attribution of ECTS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Integration in the curricula in some of the institution's programme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Integration in the curricula across the institution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Elective module on student engagement	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Recognition as a form of facilitation of students' academic life											
Scheduling of school hours	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specific status for engaged students	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Extra points	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Recognition in the form of non-academic awards for students and as a community building tool											
Valorisation of student engagement: space for associations, events	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Award	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Certificate of engagement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Recognition of the skills acquired through student engagement activities											
Validation of the skills acquired through the experience of engagement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Digital badge	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Diploma supplement mentioning the activities carried out	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Diploma supplement mentioning the skills acquired	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Training sessions for engaged students	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Financial support for student engagement											
Financial support for students-led projects	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Direct financial support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Scholarship	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-diagnosis for students

Modalities of recognition of student engagement	Implementation and use					Communication					
	Is it implemented in your University? <i>1. No 2. Yes 3. I don't know</i>	Since when does it exist?	Which students can benefit from it? (field, level)	Have you or someone you know benefited from it? <i>1. No 2. Yes 3. I don't know</i>	Are you satisfied with how it is implemented? (Ex.: Is it well balanced between the activities carried out during the engagement and the recognition?) <i>1. a little 2. moderately 3. a lot</i>	Is it important according to you ? <i>1. a little 2. moderately 3. a lot</i>	Can you easily find information on it? <i>1. No 2. Not really 3. A lot</i>	Where is it possible to find information on it? <i>1. Website of your university ; 2. Of your institute ; 3. Of your faculty ; 4. During events organised by the university/school ; 5. During events organised by the university/school ; 6. Freshers' fair ; 7. Other</i>			
Formal recognition for individual student, related to the academic life											
Attribution of ECTS	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Integration in the curricula across the institution	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Integration in the curricula in some of the institution's programme	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Elective module on student engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Recognition as a form of facilitation of students' academic life											
Scheduling of school hours	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Specific status for engaged students	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Extra points	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Recognition in the form of non-academic awards for students and as a community building tool											
Valorisation of student engagement : space for associations, events	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Award	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Certificate of engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Recognition of the skills acquired through student engagement activities											
Validation of the skills acquired through the experience of engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Digital badge	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Diploma supplement mentioning the activities carried out	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Diploma supplement mentioning the skills acquired	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Training sessions for engaged students	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Financial support for student engagement											
Financial support for students-led projects	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Direct financial support	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		
Scholarship	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7		

Staff / Teacher Diagnosis

Modalities of recognition of student engagement	Implementation and use					Communication		
	Is it implemented in your University? 1. No 2. Yes 3. I don't know	Since when does it exist?	Which students can benefit from it? (field, level)	Have you or someone you know benefited from it? 1. No 2. Yes 3. I don't know	Are you satisfied with how it is implemented? (Ex.: Is it well balanced between the activities carried out during the engagement and the recognition?) 1. A little 2. Moderately 3. A lot	Is it important according to you? 1. a little 2. moderately 3. a lot	Can you easily find information on it? 1. No 2. Not really 3. Yes	Where is it possible to find information on it? 1. Website of your university; 2. of your institute; 3. of your faculty; 4. During events organised by the university/school; 5. Conferences; 6. Freshers' fair 7. Other
Formal recognition for individual student, related to the academic life								
Attribution of ECTS	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Integration in the curricula across the institution	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Integration in the curricula in some of the institution's programme	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Elective module on student engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Recognition as a form of facilitation of students' academic life								
Scheduling of school hours	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Specific status for engaged students	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Extra points	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Recognition in the form of non-academic awards for students and as a community building tool								
Valorisation of student engagement : space for associations, events	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Award	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Certificate of engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Recognition of the skills acquired through student engagement activities								
Validation of the skills acquired through the experience of engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Digital badge	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Diploma supplement mentioning the activities carried out	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Diploma supplement mentioning the skills acquired	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Training sessions for engaged students	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Financial support for student engagement								
Financial support for students-led projects	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Direct financial support	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Scholarship	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Diagnosis for acquiring deeper knowledge on your institution's practices

Is student engagement part of your institution strategy?		Does your institution have a structure/unit/department dedicated to student engagement?		Is the activity recognised by your institution?				
				Within the framework of the institution		Beyond the framework of the institution		
No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes, and the unit is dedicated to this matter only	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes, and the unit takes charge of student engagement among other responsibilities	<input type="checkbox"/>	Activities in student associations	<input type="checkbox"/>	Activities for health promotion	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Yes, it is part of the institution's strategic plan (policy level)	<input type="checkbox"/>			No	<input type="checkbox"/>	Activities in student unions	<input type="checkbox"/>	Activities within NGOs / Associations / Youth organisations and citizenship-related activities
Yes, it is mentioned in the institution's official documents	<input type="checkbox"/>	I don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>	Artistic and cultural activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	Artistic and cultural activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Yes, it is mentioned in the institution's publications and reports (annual and diversity reports)	<input type="checkbox"/>			Mandates as student representatives	<input type="checkbox"/>	Firefighter activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Yes, it is part of the communication plan (newsletters, social networks...)	<input type="checkbox"/>			Participation to University Law Clinics	<input type="checkbox"/>	Involvement in political parties	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Yes, it is mentioned in the institution's website	<input type="checkbox"/>			Sport activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	Mandates outside the institution (e.g. representative in municipalities and other political mandates)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Yes, student engagement is a pillar for the office(s) of student life	<input type="checkbox"/>			Short-term projects or events	<input type="checkbox"/>	Mentoring activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Yes, faculties are encouraged to promote student engagement	<input type="checkbox"/>			Other activities:	<input type="checkbox"/>	Participation to religious associations	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Other strategies:							Sport activities	<input type="checkbox"/>
							Other types of organisations	<input type="checkbox"/>
							Other activities:	<input type="checkbox"/>

What are the main reasons for recognising student engagement within your institution? <i>1. Not relevant</i> <i>2. Relevant</i> <i>3. Very important</i>	Which students can benefit from student engagement recognition measures?		How would you rate the awareness of <i>1. Not good</i> <i>2. Good</i> <i>3. Very good</i>	Does your institution recognise the skills acquired through the experience of engagement?		Does your institution use skills portfolio (Europass or equivalent) for its students in the framework of the curriculum? <i>1. No ; 2. Yes ; 3. The institution is currently implementing such portfolio ; 4. I don't know</i>	
Develop citizenship	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	All students	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	No	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3 4
"Empower students" for their future lives (professional and as engaged citizens), strengthening students' academic backgrounds with the recognition of the experiences of engagement and the related skills	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	Part-time students	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	I don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Full-time students	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3	Yes, it is detailed in the diploma supplement	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		International students	<input type="checkbox"/>		Yes, it is detailed in a skill certificate	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Only for students in some programs	<input type="checkbox"/>		Yes, students are delivered digital badges for each skill	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Facilitate access to extracurricular activities for all students	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3				Other modalities of recognition:		
Facilitate student integration into the labour market	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3						
Give formal recognition to the non-disciplinary skills developed in this context	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3						
Help students develop soft skills (communication, teamwork, adaptability and flexibility, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3						
Promote student engagement and rise the number of engaged students within the institution	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3						
Reinforce the institution's social responsibilities and societal mission	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3						
Respect the legislation	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3						
Revitalise the university campus and the university student life	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 2 3						
Other reasons:							